

OPTIMIZATION OF THE METHOD OF BRACHIAL PLEXUS NERVES BLOCKADE USING ULTRASONIC NAVIGATION

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Abstract. *It is important to suggest that brachial plexus block is a generally accepted method of anesthesia and analgesia in upper limb surgery and is widely used by physicians [2,5,9]. However, the classical approach to the brachial plexus has its advantages and disadvantages depending on the individual characteristics of patients and the area of surgical intervention. Therefore, the choice of the most appropriate method of brachial plexus block is crucial to prevent complications [7,8]. The frequency of peripheral nerve damage in trauma and somatic diseases, according to various authors, is 25-65%, with the most common post-traumatic nature of damage to the nerves of the upper limbs - 41.9%. A significant proportion of these injuries are combined nerve injuries observed in the lower third of the forearm (58.4% of cases).*

Keywords: *brachial plexus block, nerve injuries, regional anesthesia, US navigation, ultravisualization.*

It is known to everyone that in the last decade, the idea of the possibility of using peripheral regional anesthesia in patients with peripheral nerve injuries has changed significantly. This was facilitated by the study of the possibilities and wider implementation of ultrasound navigation (US navigation), which allows for control over the procedure and more precise delivery of the anesthetic to the blocked nerve structures [1,5,8].

Definitely, the possibility of ultrasound visualization of the main vessels, brachial plexus and dynamic control over the course of anesthesia increases the safety of invasive interventions, and the incidence of complications, according to the literature, decreases to 2.5%. Interventional pain relief procedures have traditionally been performed under the control of fluoroscopy, computed tomography (CT) or MRI. The use of ultrasound is explained by its numerous advantages over other visualization methods, including ease of implementation, the absence of ionizing radiation, better visualization of soft tissues (e.g. muscles, ligaments) and blood vessels, visualization of needle advancement in real time and, sometimes, the ability to observe the spread of the injected drug [6,8,10]. In this regard, the search for ways to optimize puncture under ultrasound control is important.

Purpose of the study. Study of the anatomical and topographic features of the brachial plexus in healthy people to optimize the block technique using ultrasound navigation.

Material and methods of the study. Ultrasound examination was performed on 40 volunteers (including 24 (60.0%) men and 16 (40.0%) women) using an Aplio 500 ultrasound scanner with a high-frequency linear sensor of 7-17 MHz, which allowed us to determine the structure of the nerve, differentiate the nerve from surrounding tissues and vessels. The exception for the study were individuals with anatomical abnormalities or diseases of the nervous system. In the study of the nerves of the brachial plexus, we used the standard technique of conducting a bilateral ultrasound examination (Eskin N.A., 2008; Saltikova V.G., 2011) in the clavicular, supraclavicular and axillary regions. We identified the main nerve trunks and topographic

landmarks (subclavian artery, vein, ribs, muscles), assessed parameters such as depth, thickness of the nerve trunks, distance between them and vascular structures.

Certainly, in grayscale mode, the nerve was assessed according to the standard scheme (contours, size, shape, echo structure, echogenicity), if necessary, panoramic scanning of the nerve trunk was performed, and then we moved on to Dopplerographic assessment (color-coded modes, pulsed-wave Dopplerography).

Results of the study. For determining the echogenicity of the nerve, it was compared with the tissue of the tendons and unchanged sections of the nerve under study or with the nerve on the opposite (healthy) limb.

While obtaining optimal ultrasound images of nerves in B-mode using color Doppler mapping, the presence of vessels in the visualized structures was determined, then pulsed-wave Dopplerography was used to differentiate vessels with arterial and venous blood flow spectra. During longitudinal scanning, the nerve fiber was an alternation of hypo- and hyperechoic linear structures surrounded by a hyperechoic membrane; during transverse scanning, the nerve fiber looked like a honeycomb (multiple hypoechoic inclusions - nervous tissue, surrounded by hyperechoic membranes - connective tissue). During ultrasound examination, depending on the localization of the brachial plexus, the ultrasound picture during transverse scanning was in the form of rounded or ellipsoid, predominantly hypoechoic formations, and in the axillary region, the nerve trunks were represented by a heterogeneous structure in the form of a honeycomb. Unlike plexuses, peripheral nerves appear, when scanned longitudinally, as alternating hypo- and hyperechoic linear structures surrounded by a hyperechoic membrane; when scanned transversely, the nerve fiber appears as a honeycomb: multiple hypoechoic inclusions nerve tissue are surrounded by hyperechoic membranes-connective tissue.

In bilateral ultrasound examination, the surrounding soft tissues were characterized by the symmetry of the echographic picture.

As part of the study, the following segments of the brachial plexus were studied in detail in 40 healthy volunteers: interscalene, supraclavicular, subclavian and axillary. The following results were obtained:

Interscalene segment: the nerve trunks of the brachial plexus were located in the space between the anterior and middle scalene muscles. The average depth was 1.5 ± 0.3 cm, and the diameter of the upper trunk was 2.1 ± 0.2 mm.

In order to visualize this segment, a longitudinal projection of the ultrasound sensor was used, oriented along the scalene muscles.

Supraclavicular segment: the nerve structures were clearly visualized in the supraclavicular fossa, located lateral to the subclavian artery. The average depth was 1.7 ± 0.4 cm. The distance between the trunks and vascular structures varied from 3.4 ± 0.3 mm to 5.2 ± 0.5 mm, which required increased attention to prevent vascular damage.

Subclavian segment: in the subclavian region, the nerve trunks were located medial to the subclavian artery and were clearly visualized with an oblique projection of the transducer. The thickness of the nerve structures varied from 2.3 ± 0.3 mm to 3.0 ± 0.4 mm, with an average depth of 1.9 ± 0.3 cm.

Axillary segment: in the axillary region, the brachial plexus nerves surrounded the axillary artery and vein, located relatively superficially. The average depth was 1.8 ± 0.4 cm, which ensured good visualization with a linear transducer.

In overweight individuals, the depth increased by an average of 0.5 cm compared to patients with normal body weight.

The average diameter of the nerve structures varied from 2.2 ± 0.2 mm (upper trunk) to 3.1 ± 0.4 mm (lower trunk). In men, the nerve diameter was slightly larger (3.2 ± 0.3 mm) compared to women (2.9 ± 0.3 mm), which is associated with greater overall muscle mass.

However, in the supraclavicular region, the brachial plexus was clearly visualized between the anterior and middle scalene muscles, with the adjacent subclavian artery. In the axillary region, the nerves were located near the axillary artery and vein, which required additional Doppler control to prevent vascular complications.

Distance between structures: between the upper and middle trunks of the brachial plexus, the average distance was 4.1 ± 0.5 mm, between the nerve trunks and the subclavian artery, the average distance was 3.5 ± 0.3 mm.

Additionally, in 8% of the examined patients, a high degree of branching of the brachial plexus was observed, which made it difficult to visualize individual nerve trunks. In 12%, changes in the course of the subclavian artery were detected, which required a change in the standard point of needle insertion.

The topographic location of the nerves in this area will allow successful administration of the anesthetic with a minimal risk of vascular complications. Thus, the interscalene block can be performed during surgical interventions on the clavicle, shoulder, shoulder joint, and forearm. The patient was placed on his back with a small bolster under the shoulders. The head was turned in the direction opposite to the block at an angle of 35 degrees to the sagittal plane. The ultrasound sensor was installed at the level of the cricoid cartilage, perpendicular to the interscalene groove. The main ultrasound landmarks are the common carotid artery, the internal jugular vein, and the anterior and middle scalene muscles located outside of them.

Between the muscles, the nerve structures are visualized in cross-section as rounded hypoechoic formations.

Supraclavicular block can be performed in patients undergoing shoulder surgery, as well as in the forearm and hand when distal blocks cannot be performed. To visualize the brachial plexus in the supraclavicular region, the ultrasound sensor was installed at an angle along the upper edge of the clavicle. The main landmark was the subclavian artery, determined above the level of the first rib. The nerve structures of the brachial plexus in this area in cross-section often look like a single bundle, located laterally and cranially to the subclavian artery.

Inferoclavicular block can be performed during surgical interventions on the upper limbs distal to the upper third of the shoulder. When performing a brachial plexus block using the inferoclavicular approach using ultrasonography, the device sensor was installed perpendicular to the lower edge of the clavicle in the parasagittal plane. This position allows visualization of the neurovascular bundle going to the axillary region in a perpendicular plane.

Moreover, auxiliary block can be used during surgical interventions, distal to the lower third of the shoulder. The sensor was positioned perpendicularly in the axillary cavity. The ultrasound image identified a pulsating brachial artery, which is not compressed when pressure is applied by the sensor. The median, radial and ulnar nerves are located around it.

Conclusions. By summarizing it should be suggested that the use of ultrasound navigation significantly improves the accuracy of the brachial plexus nerve block; the obtained data on the

topographic features allowed us to develop optimal parameters for performing the procedure; the proposed technique can also be used as a standard for regional anesthesia.

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